

D3.2 Recommendations for the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy

Una.Resin Project Deliverable D3.2

Final Version, 6th June 2024; Lead Authors: Una.Resin WP3 Team (*Uniwersytet Jagielloński w Krakowie*: Elżbieta Binczycka-Gacek, Bartosz Brożek; *Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne*: Ekaterina Smoliakova, Severine Bortot; *KU Leuven*: Wannes Ribbens, Veerle Bruggeman)

Contents

Executive Summary	3
1. Background and assumptions	3
1.1 Lessons learned	4
1.2 Other assumptions.....	5
2. Goals and instruments.....	7
2.1 Goals.....	7
2.2 Instruments	9
3. Threats and opportunities	10
4. Best practices & potential actions	11

Executive Summary

These Recommendations collect ideas for the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy elaborated within the Horizon 2020 'Una.Resin' project carried out by the Una Europa partner universities. The document describes the background of the present Recommendations as well as the assumptions they are based on (Section 1). It proceeds to identify five goals – pertaining to career path development, performance assessment, employees' well-being, employees' engagement with society, and the support for early-career researchers – which should be considered for the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy.

The document also identifies a number of instruments the Alliance may utilise to further the goals (Section 2). In Section 3, some key challenges and opportunities connected to human capital development and the position of Una Europa are listed, which should inform any considerations on the future strategy. Finally, Section 4, considered as a 'living' part of the document, can be enriched with new insights, collects existing best practices and ideas for potential actions to be considered when the future Strategy and its Implementation Plan are developed.

Thus, the goal of these Recommendations is not to offer a precise outline of the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy, but rather to provide a comprehensive background which will constitute an important point of reference for the future policy decisions of the Alliance in the area of human capital development, including the adoption of the Strategy.

1. Background and assumptions

Una Europa is an Alliance of eleven leading research-intensive universities, which aim at creating a European inter-university environment by triggering institutionalised cooperation in education, research, and societal outreach. Una Europa has the objective to transform the institutional framework of its member institutions to prepare for the next wave of global challenges.

Through the three-year Horizon 2020 'Una.Resin' project, Una Europa is determining the purpose and areas for future research collaborations, within and beyond Una Europa. Una.Resin partners are creating strategies for Research & Innovation agendas, opening up and sharing Research Infrastructure and Resources, and strengthening Human Capital. Within the Una.Resin project, the Alliance will also develop, implement, and evaluate pilot actions for the systematic support for excellence as well as create cross -disciplinary and crosssectoral teams.

The purpose of this document is to use the findings of the mapping exercise, workshops, and discussions carried out within the Una.Resin project in order to formulate some recommendations for the future Una Europa human capital development strategy.

1.1 Lessons learned

These Recommendations are based on the outcomes of the mapping exercise on HR (Human Resources) strategies conducted within Una.Resin project¹ as well as three co-creation workshops organised in June and July 2022 in Paris, Krakow, and Madrid². The main findings of those activities include the following³:

- all Una Europa partners have developed complex human capital development ecosystems and have well developed HR strategies, but there are areas where these mechanisms can be strengthened, also by learning from each other;
- the human capital development frameworks at the Una Europa universities share some challenging aspects: the lack of diversification in career development paths; a more quantitative than qualitative performance assessment process; the unclear nature and goals of performance assessment; institutional divide between the systems supporting the employees' well-being and the systems promoting and protecting other values; complex infrastructure supporting business-academia cooperation as well as infrastructure for open science, with a relative lack of communication and incentives in this area; and significant struggle with embedding team science, interdisciplinarity and citizen science into the mainstream activities of the universities. Naturally, not all Una Europa partner universities share all of the above-mentioned challenges to the same degree, and, in various areas, different partners have developed innovative mechanisms which may be transferrable to other partners;
- at the strategic and planning level, the decision-makers consider restructuring the human capital development system to find a better solution regarding the employment of young researchers (post-doc level), and rethinking the performance assessment system to capture more the qualitative rather than only quantitative aspects of job performance;
- the decision-makers tend to overlook the need for a change in the communication procedures connected to career paths and performance assessment;
- academics are generally satisfied with their careers and workplace, and have a good general knowledge of the institutional framework with relation to the human capital development strategy of their university;
- in the perception of the academics the fields where further development is needed include a more elaborate and better communicated career path development system, the development of a fairer performance assessment procedure, and more emphasis on the well-being support framework;

¹ Deliverable 3.1 of the 'Una.Resin' project: Mapping HR Strategies and priorities for joint strategy. The goal of the mapping exercise was to identify and analyse the key elements of the human capital development frameworks of the Una Europa partner universities in the areas of career path development, performance assessment, and diversity and equality. The exercise also covered issues connected to interlocking research activities with the broader university ecosystem. The exercise was based on the triangulation of methods: document analysis, interviews with university management, and online survey for researchers.

² Within the lifetime of the Una.Resin project, three co-creation workshops were organised: 'Excellent Research and Beyond' in Madrid on June 20th-21st, 2022; 'Creative Environment for Happy People' in Kraków on June 27th-28th, 2022; and 'Breaking Down Boundaries With & For Society' in Paris on July 1st, 2022. The outcomes of the co-creation workshops are reflected in the recommendations below, in particular with regards to Goals 3 and 4.

³ The conclusions provided below are taken from the Mapping HR Strategies and priorities for joint strategy, cf. fn 1.

- the academics clearly struggle with some dimensions of the existing frameworks; in particular, their judgment is that team work and interdisciplinarity is not sufficiently supported at their institutions; similarly, their evaluation of citizen science initiatives is low; this may be either an outcome of problems in communication (the employees do not know or understand what the goals of their institution are in this context or how those goals are to be realised) or of structural issues in the framework itself.

These findings strongly suggest the need for further actions and development, in particular in the following areas:

- the universities should intensify their work on efficient communication channels, which not only provide information, but help employees to understand the common goals and the formats to achieve them;
- there is a space for significant development in the area of the career path model, which should be more diversified, as well as individualised;
- the performance assessment criteria and procedures should also be modified to include a more holistic and individualised approach, i.e., the assessment should include in a balanced way all the dimensions of the academic's work (research, teaching, business cooperation, societal outreach, management tasks), as well as serve not only as a decision-making aid for the university management, but also as a tool for supporting the individual development of the academics;
- the universities should put more emphasis on developing and explaining the framework for the promotion and protection of well-being;
- the universities should be clearer and more transparent in their strategies, support systems, and assessment criteria about the nature and importance of team cooperation and interdisciplinarity;
- the universities, while already providing sufficient infrastructure for business-academia cooperation and open access, should put more emphasis in this context on communication, incentivisation, coordination and soft skills;
- the universities should rethink their strategies pertaining to citizen science and invest in communication and support systems for relevant activities, to help employees realise and understand why citizen science is important.

1.2 Other assumptions

The Recommendations for the future Una Europa human capital development strategy must take into consideration and align with the existing foundational documents of the Alliance, and in particular **Una Europa 2030 Strategy**⁴. Of particular importance is Una Europa's commitment to values such as diversity and human dignity, academic freedom, and individual well-being, as well as the fact that Una Europa aims to develop an inclusive inter-university community, which empowers students, academics, and professional staff to act as active contributors and co-creators, while creating a common sense of belonging. This commitment

⁴ <https://www.una-europa.eu/stories/una-europa-2030-strategy-shaping-our-shared-future-for-the-better>

is visible not only in the Una Europa foundational documents, but also in various joint undertakings, and in particular in the work of the Una Europa Diversity Council.

Moreover, the joint actions of Una Europa are to generate ‘**added value**’, i.e., to achieve goals which are not – or are not to such an extent – achievable through the unilateral actions of the partner universities. Therefore, the joint endeavours should be developed in areas where the collaborative effort of the Una Europa partners would be particularly valuable; with regard to issues where the voice of the entire Alliance would be particularly important; in the areas where particularly bold actions and out-of-the-box thinking is needed; and in connection to issues where policy makers, and in particular European policy-makers, may be influenced by a joint Una Europa action.

These Recommendations also reflect the existing **charter of the European Commission**. In particular, as stated in the *Commission Recommendation of 11 March 2005 on the European for Researchers and on a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers*⁵, researchers should be provided a supportive research environment and working culture, where individuals and research groups are valued, encouraged and supported, and provided with the necessary material and intangible support to enable them to fulfil their objectives and tasks; and that the recruitment methods and career evaluation/appraisal systems should constitute a transparent, open, equal and internationally accepted system of recruitment and career development. The new European Framework for Research Careers and the revised Charter for Researchers both emphasize the need for diversified and flexible career paths, holistic performance assessments, and robust support for early-career researchers. The European framework’s focus on interdisciplinary and intersectoral mobility, improved recruitment and working conditions, and comprehensive career development aligns with Una Europa’s goals of creating individualized career paths and balancing qualitative and quantitative performance metrics. Furthermore, both the European initiatives and Una Europa’s strategy prioritize inclusiveness, well-being, and societal engagement, ensuring a supportive and innovative research environment. By integrating these elements, Una Europa can enhance its strategy to align with broader European research policies, addressing key challenges and leveraging opportunities for its member institutions.

Moreover, *The Council of the European Union Recommendations on a Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe and the European Research Area Policy Agenda: Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024*⁶ defined priority areas for joint actions, which include: Open Science (support for an open science culture across the Union - support the developing of open science skills; consider differences in disciplines, take into account multilingualism and cultural differences); Research Careers (promote attractive and sustainable research careers, balanced talent circulation and international, transdisciplinary, and inter-sectoral mobility across the ERA; ensure gender equality, equal opportunities for all, and inclusiveness; give greater attention to early and mid-stage careers; provide clear, more diverse, merit-based career paths and guidance to make informed career choices; equip researchers with the training and skills required (skills provided to doctoral candidates are too often focused on careers within academia); Research assessment system (reform a research assessment

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2005:075:0067:0077:EN:PDF>

⁶ <https://european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/policy-agenda-2022-2024>

system to reward quality, impact, open science practices, leadership and engagement with society and collaboration with industry); Bring Science closer to Citizens.

It should be added that the Una Europa partner universities are already following many of the abovementioned recommendations of the Commission, in particular with some of them having received the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) label and implementing the HRS4R action plans. The HRS4R is a European Commission initiative designed to support institutions in implementing the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. This strategy aims to improve the working conditions, career development opportunities, and overall environment for researchers in Europe. The HRS4R framework promotes open, transparent, and merit-based recruitment processes, which are essential for fostering an inclusive and supportive research environment. These principles align closely with Una Europa's goals of enhancing career path development, performance assessment, and the well-being of researchers.

Several Una Europa partners have received the HRS4R award, including Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna, Jagiellonian University, KU Leuven, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, and University College Dublin. This recognition underscores their commitment to high standards in human resources practices, providing a model for other Una Europa institutions to follow. By integrating the HRS4R framework, Una Europa can ensure that its human capital development strategy aligns with best practices across Europe, enhancing its ability to attract and retain top research talent and fostering a competitive and inclusive research environment. The Una Europa partner universities can - where necessary and desired - help and strengthen each other in implementing HRS4R by jointly reflecting on the ambitions and formulated action plans, and by sharing good practices. In this way, HRS4R becomes a real framework towards shared actions and ambitions.

Finally, the present Recommendations also consider the current trends in HR research, which include the emphasis on the use of innovative technology in the work environment, the shift towards impermanence and adaptation in the organisation of work (project-based and cyclical approaches), shared governance, the necessity to develop trust and sense of belonging, the importance of mental health and well-being, and the growing need for re-skilling and re-training for all staff categories.

2. Goals and instruments

2.1 Goals

The below specified goals provide a broad spectrum of issues which, assessed against the background of the assumptions of these Recommendations (Section 1), constitute a key challenge in the area of human capital development in the near and more distant future of universities.

It is not suggested that all of those goals should be addressed by the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy; nor is it suggested that the selected goals should be

realised to the same degree of ambition. It may not be possible given the existing and future constraints: legal, organisational, or financial. Moreover, one of the assumptions specified above reads that Una Europa should undertake joint actions only when there is an added value to acting together and when the action is beneficial to all partners.

Arguably, however, it is reasonable to provide a comprehensive list of goals related to human capital development as such a coherent and broad picture will facilitate future policy-related considerations at the level of the Alliance and the implementation of joint formats. Still, all the goals outlined below are connected to some challenges which may potentially be addressed by Una Europa to jointly generate added value.

The analysis of the outcomes of the mapping exercise (see Section 1 above), as well as the ongoing academic and policy-related discussion pertaining to human capital development in the Higher Education sector, reveals that there are five aspects of the human capital development system which generate the biggest challenges for the future: career path development, performance assessment, societal engagement, employees' well-being, and the development of support mechanisms for early-stage researchers. It is therefore suggested that the future Una Europa human capital development strategy takes into consideration these challenges as encapsulated in the following goals:

Goal 1. Una Europa will be at the forefront of creating and experimenting with new career path development models, which would reflect the need to:

- introduce transparent, differentiated, and flexible career paths, both for teachers and researchers, as well as members of the professional services staff;
- develop and introduce a concept of individualisation of career path development for their researchers, teachers, and professional staff members;
- provide a wide range of skills development programmes, including core and soft skills, leadership skills, as well as skills helpful in individuals flourishing, aligned with the career path model;
- develop standards and tools for efficient communication of the issues connected to career path development.

Goal 2. Una Europa will be engaged in the search for a more comprehensive performance assessment system, which would reflect the need to:

- enrich the human capital development policies with the key distinction between periodical and ongoing research assessment models - the former to inform strategic level decisions, the latter aimed at helping the employee flourish⁷;
- find a balance between quantitative and qualitative performance assessment;
- include business-academia cooperation and societal outreach more prominently in the performance assessment criteria;
- reflect the differences in scientific disciplines, career paths and stages in the performance assessment criteria.

⁷ For details see Mapping HR Strategies and priorities for joint strategy, fn 1.

Goal 3. Una Europa will become a leader in making employees' well-being the highest priority in the workplace by:

- putting more emphasis on developing employee-friendly physical and digital workspaces;
- further developing the work environment and culture to encourage creativity, informed by the values of rationality and humility;
- providing employees with a better work-life balance;
- providing employees with regular as well as crisis intervention psychological support.

Goal 4. Una Europa will encourage employees to work for and with society by:

- clearly recognising the importance of societal engagement and encouraging it;
- providing employees with the understanding of and skills for societal engagement and citizen science;
- developing and experimenting with innovative tools for societal outreach.

Goal 5. Una Europa will be particularly focused on developing the next generation of researchers by:

- providing early-stage researchers with more individualised and stronger administrative support.
- developing diversified career paths for early-stage researchers and communicating them clearly;
- providing early-stage researchers with skills needed to deal with the challenges of the future;
- providing early-stage researchers with opportunities to develop their skills in a truly international, intercultural environment.

As noted above, it is not suggested that the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy should treat all the above-mentioned goals equally. In particular, given the Alliance's ambitions and the already existing strategic documents such as the Una Europa 2030 Strategy (cf. fn 4), Goal 5 (Una Europa will be particularly focused on developing the next generation of researchers) should be seen as particularly relevant for future joint actions. There is also much alignment between Goals 3 and 4 and the work already undertaken within the Alliance. On the other hand, the potential realisation of Goal 2 may be significantly limited due to the differences in the legal frameworks within which different partner universities operate. However, even in the context of the goals which may currently be seen as less relevant for the entire Alliance, there may be actions (such as debates, the sharing of best practices and standards, and joint research) which may generate added value and be beneficial for the partner universities.

2.2 Instruments

The realisation of the above-mentioned goals within the framework of Una Europa requires the use of tools and methods which are suitable for inter-university cooperation and joint action, as well as capable of generating the 'added value' referred to in the Background &

Assumptions (Section 1) above. Given these ramifications, it is proposed that the following types of instruments may be used:

- **know-how and format transfer:** Una Europa universities share their know-how within and beyond the Alliance;
- **knowledge and standards generation:** joint development of solutions to Human Capital Development challenges;
- **skills development programmes:** joint programme at developing skills of employees;
- **knowledge dissemination:** tools and formats for sharing the knowledge of, generating interest in, and stimulating debates pertaining to the key issues in human capital development among employees as well as the general public;
- **lobbying:** joint communications aimed at the decision-makers at national and European levels.

3. Threats and opportunities

There exist both threats to the full realisation of the above stated goals, as well as opportunities which may result in substantial, if not ground-breaking developments.

The **threats** include, among others:

- a) The differences in the human capital development systems between the Una Europa partner universities largely resulting from national legal regulations. This makes the adoption of common principles as well as know-how exchange difficult. The remedy may be either to lobby for relevant legal changes at both national and European levels or adopt joint standards to serve as the basis for creating a common human capital development environment within differing legal settings.
- b) Differences in work culture. Undoubtedly, there exists significant differences between work culture in different European countries. Therefore, even the adoption of the same regulations does not necessarily lead to the creation of genuinely common standards. The remedy to this threat is to try to better understand other work cultures and learn from one another. Dialogue and mutual experience are key to understanding other perspectives and ultimately enriching one's own work culture. This, in turn, may lead to shared views and common approaches. Cultures do change and converge, but the changes are evolutionary rather than revolutionary.
- c) The difficulty in introducing substantial changes in the fragile workplace environment. The workplace is usually characterised by subtle balance, which is easy to disturb. Thus, any changes to the work environment should be introduced carefully, in the spirit of dialogue and with emphasis on mutual understanding of the reasons for, and goal of the introduced novelties.
- d) The institutional inertia resulting from the difficulties in the collaboration of 11 institutions from different countries. It is difficult to manage one university. It is much more difficult to coordinate actions with the involvement of 11 universities. In order to do so, one needs to avoid drastic changes, while keeping the level of ambition high.
- e) Limited resources, both financial and human. In order to bring about changes in a complex HR ecosystem such as Una Europa's, adequate financial and human

resources are needed. These should be sufficient to meet the high ambitions of the Alliance.

The **opportunities** include, among others:

- a) The pooling of expertise and know-how from different organisational cultures. The diversity of the HR ecosystems of the Una Europa partners and the differing viewpoints the partners can offer, as well as the expertise the partners can bring to the table, constitute a unique opportunity to generate innovative ideas and find ground-breaking solutions.
- b) The opportunity to use European frameworks (European Charter, Code of Conduct, HRS4R, European framework for the assessment of researchers) as a shared framework and as a basis to develop joint ambitions, actions and initiatives.
- c) The ability to learn from the best practices. The environment consisting of 11 leading European universities is a source of some of the best practices in HR to be found in European higher education. It makes it possible to learn from each other, transfer successful action formats, and jointly improve existing solutions.
- d) The ability to test solutions on a large scale, in different environments. Una Europa offers a perfect and unique opportunity to develop and test HR related formats in a vast, rich, and differentiated work environment and learn from these experiments.
- e) Access to huge databases. Together, Una Europa universities have access to huge databases relevant for HR research and HR decision-making. The use of new technologies such as machine learning may help to uncover meaningful patterns in the databases, naturally within the limits imposed by existing legal regulations. This, in turn, may provide foundations for creating new, innovative ways of addressing HR challenges.
- f) The importance of a position developed jointly by 11 leading European universities. Una Europa is in a perfect place to influence decision-making at both national and European levels, since any position agreed upon and adopted jointly by 11 leading European universities, as well as action formats successfully tested by Una Europa, should constitute an important point of reference for political decision-makers.

4. Best practices & potential actions

Below, in order to provide an illustration of how the goals stated above may be realised, as well as to collect some ideas for particular actions which may be useful in the preparation of the future Una Europa Human Capital Development Strategy, the two tables collect:

- the relevant best practices existing in the Una Europa partner universities which are transferrable and/or scalable;
- some ideas for potential actions, which transpired from discussions carried out within the Una.Resin project.

This part of the Recommendations should be seen as a 'living document'. The tables may be extended with new examples of the best practices as well as the new ideas for potential actions. The Research Career and Culture Cluster is entrusted with this task.

Table 1: Identified best practices

Best practice	Short description	Goals achieved
'CONTRACT WITH THE DEAN'	Activation of professors through individual 'contracts' with deans. These contracts are not similar to plans of personal development as they are focused on professors defining 'institutional' goals that are important for the faculty/university as a whole.	1,4
MENTORING	Encouraging senior/experienced faculty members to become involved in the mentoring of younger personnel (in the context of development/promotion plans) can be a good opportunity to implement a system of internal mentoring. Another example is UCM's mentoring programme, aimed at both predoctoral and postdoctoral recruits. Its objective is to form early-stage researchers who are interested in career options beyond the traditional academic career, with highly qualified mentors working in professional environments outside of academia.	1,5
EXAMPLES OF EXCELLENCE	It is a good practice to provide "examples of excellence" for people applying for promotion together with the descriptions of the posts/successive levels.	1,5
BIOSKETCH	Using a 'substantial' CV or biosketch to complement the quantitative data in research assessment is a good way to introduce aspects of qualitative assessment.	2
DIFFERENTIATED ASSESSMENT CRITERIA	Use of different criteria of assessment depending on the degree and career stage. For example, moving to higher positions in the organisational structure, one initially expects 3 "standard criteria" of research, teaching, and service; above that one also expects advising, leadership competences; while at the following level of career development one includes science and technology transfer.	1,2,4
FIGHTING PREJUDICE	A training course for senior academic staff on bias and prejudice.	3,4
INTERDISCIPLINARY FLAGSHIPS/THEMES	Establishing cross-faculty research communities and adopting university-level interdisciplinary research themes.	1,3,4
PSI-CALL	PsiCall is a telematic psychological counselling service that aims to meet the psychosocial needs of students and employees of the Complutense University of Madrid. The main channel of communication to provide this service differs according to the characteristics of each demand and the preference of the callers, with the telephone being PsiCall's main tool, supported by chat and email. This allows the service to give quick responses to urgent problems and to provide guidance, counselling and psychological care. The team is made up of a group of experts in emergency, crisis, and telephone psychology, with experience in clinical practice.	3,5
SKILLS PROGRAMME & BROCHURE (YOURECA)	To support research staff to develop a wide range of professional knowledge and skills.	1,2,5
YOUNG RESEARCHERS CAREER CENTER	To support early-career researchers at KU Leuven (PhDs, postdocs, and tenure track professors) with information, inspiration, motivation, and guidance to empower them to make their own conscious career decisions: self-reflection tools; career workshops; career guidance; career & networking events.	5
MENTAL HEALTH MATTERS	Podcast for and by KU Leuven researchers. In different episodes, talks with other PhD students and postdocs about their mental well-being, covering topics such as anxiety, work-life balance, and social connection. This will include a Podcast club covering themes from the podcast series, providing opportunities to share experiences, connect with other participants, and discuss mental well-being.	3

INTERSECTORAL MOBILITY – COOPERATION WITH THE NON-ACADEMIC LABOUR MARKET	Includes: (a) the Flemish Universities PhD Talent Pool is a career and jobsite for all PhD candidates and postdocs of the five Flemish universities and beyond; (b) yearly inter-university job markets for young researchers; (c) a Stakeholders Engagement Panel to build connections with the external labour market.	4,5
NETWORK OF LOCAL NEARBY CONFIDANTS	For a confidential conversation about your health and well-being with someone outside your own working environment (KU Leuven).	3
ISUPERVISE	KU Leuven wants to support its new Senior Academic Staff members (ZAP) as much as possible in their role as supervisor of a research team. Supervisors have an important role at our university. In order to help make the supervisor role successful, we organise a masterclass to support you in your leadership development. In this masterclass we will provide information on the tasks and responsibilities this new role entails. We will also create the opportunity to interact with colleagues with more or less experience in supervising researchers.	1,5
AD HOC STATUS FOR EARLY-CAREER RESEARCHERS	A specific status was created in Paris 1 for the earlycareer researchers who do not have a post-PhD or other contract with the university but would like to use universities' resources for their own research. To secure and unify the welcoming of these researchers, a special legal framework was created through a welcoming agreement.	5
CAREER MOBILITY ADVISOR	In Paris 1, a position of a career mobility advisor was recently created. The president of the university nominates to this position a senior researcher who is discharged of 1/3 of their teaching hours to guide and advise academic staff on internal and external career mobility.	1
RESEARCH ONTOLOGY AND INTEGRITY COURSE FOR PHD STUDENTS	Conditioned by national framework for PhD studies, a MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses) on research on ontology and integrity was developed in Paris 1.	1, 4

Table 2: Ideas for potential actions

Potential Action	Short description	Goals achieved
UNA EUROPA CERTIFICATES	A system of certificates awarded by Una Europa according to the model developed in the team science pilot action of Una.Resin.	1, 3, 4, 5
UNA EUROPA BLUEPRINT FOR CREATING AN INDIVIDUAL CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLAN	A set of recommendations, instructions, checklists, and other tools to aid researchers (especially early-stage researchers) in composing their individual career development plan.	1, 5
CO-CREATION WORKSHOP ON INCORPORATING 3 RD MISSION INTO PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT	Organisation of a (series of) workshops with the participation of HR specialists, researchers, and professional staff members to develop testable formats for assessing 3rd mission involvement.	2, 4
A BLUEPRINT FOR THE INTEGRATED SKILLS OF THE RESEARCHER OF	An Una Europa document looking at the (more distant) future of research and identifying the kinds of skills which will be essential for a successful research career in the decades to come, with suggestions of how to develop those skills.	1,5

THE FUTURE		
A DEDICATED SERVICE FOR MATCHMAKING AND CAREER OPPORTUNITIES FOR EARLY-STAGE RESEARCHERS	Development of an Una Europa 'meeting point' for young researchers, where they can share information and know-how, and find potential collaborators	5

